

Pediatrician's View...

Say No to Junks

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The consumption of junk food has grown on an alarming rate among the Indian children over the last few decades. India is facing a growing epidemic of non-communicable diseases (NCDs), like diabetes mellitus, obesity, cardiovascular diseases (hypertension, ischemic heart disease and stroke), and cancers. These diseases have their roots engraved in the unhealthy eating habits, tobacco use, alcohol use and physical inactivity. The incidence of obesity in children is on a steep rise in India, the number of obese children have doubled in 5 years according to NFHS 2015-16. Obesity is a disease in itself and a precursor to many non-communicable diseases.

Ministry women and child development in 2015 used the term **“high in fats, salts, sugar (HFSS)”** instead junk food to define *“any foods (food or drink, packed or non-packed, processed or non-processed) which contains little or limited presence of proteins, vitamins, phytochemicals, minerals and dietary fiber but are rich in fat (saturated fatty acids), salt and sugar and high in energy (calories) that are known to have negative impact on health if consumed regularly or in high amounts. Junk food may also contain carbonated beverages”*

Adolescence is an important period of life, habits and lifestyle formed in this period are carried out throughout life. Adolescents are easily influenced by peers, media, and celebrities. The rational part of brain develops slowly than the impulsive part, thus impulsivity takes precedence over the adolescent decisions. Rationality and right judgment is achieved by the second decade of life.

Therefore, adolescents more often enjoy risk-taking behaviour which give them a kick. This leads to trying tobacco, drugs, smoking, alcohol and fast foods. They want to experiment and in a quest of independence, like to try out new things. They feel eating out is a social status symbol. This has led to very high consumption of junk food in adolescents. A study among adolescents of New Delhi documented that 93% eat packaged food and 68% consume sugar-sweetened beverages more than once a week; 53% consume these products at least once a day. Almost one-fourth consume ultra-processed food HFSS such as burger and pizza, more than once a week.

Junk food consumption is motivated by many factors, including:

- easy availability,
- palatability,
- working parents,
- attractive presentation,
- catchy advertisements,
- nuclear families,
- online/digital ordering and home delivery,
- urbanization,
- low cost, and
- vigorous marketing strategies.

Consumption of fast foods can lead to obesity and its associated complications, dental caries, allergies, and risk of cancer due to carcinogenic properties of some food additives. Energy drinks also have added adverse effects due to their high caffeine content leading to neurological and psychiatric symptoms, and cardiac dysrhythmias. Binge eating with screen viewing leads to hazardous effects on health in

the form of obesity, and this is further compounded by low physical activity. Apart from these effects they lack the personal touch and care, may be unclean, unhygienic, adulterated and overall too costly as compared to homemade food.

To address this burning issue, the Indian Academy of Pediatrics released its guidelines on the Fast and Junk Foods, Sugar Sweetened Beverages, and Energy Drinks for the prevention of chronic NCDs, including obesity and metabolic syndrome. A new term “**JUNCS**” was coined to encompass all the foods which are undesirable either in the nutrient content (in terms of calories, fats, sugar, or salt), or quality (in terms of processing, packaging, preservation, preparation or storage); hyper palatable foods (which may be consumed in large quantities); and foods containing toxic substances such as caffeine, additives or colors.

- **J: Junk foods (high in fats, salts, sugar HFSS)**
- **U: Ultra processed foods**
- **N: Nutritionally inappropriate foods**
- **C: Caffeinated/coloured/carbonated beverages**
- **S: Sugar sweetened beverages (SSBs)**

A pan Indian survey by CSE in 13,274 school children in the age group 9–17 years from 123 districts concluded that almost every child consumed packaged sugar-sweetened beverages (92.1%), salted packaged food (94.3 %) and sweet packaged food (95.1%). Every second child (53%) consumed packaged food or beverages at least once a day. The most common junk food items reportedly consumed are samosa,

patties, burgers, manchurian, noodles, pizza, chips, chocolate, bakery products, soft drinks, sugar-sweetened beverages, and caffeinated drinks.

Guidelines for Children and Families

1. General Recommendations

- Avoid consumption of the JUNCS foods and beverages by all children and adolescents, as far as possible.
- Alternatively, limit consumption of the JUNCS foods at home/outside and suggest to have not more than one serving per week; serving not exceeding 50% of total daily energy intake for that age.
- Do not consume foods while watching television/screen.
- The recommendations endorse WHO guidelines to eliminate trans-fat and reduce free sugars to <5% of total energy intake.
- Freshly cooked home foods with minimal addition of sugar and no trans-fats should be preferred over restaurant/packaged foods.
- Traditional and acceptable home-made snacks with long shelf-life can be offered to children as alternative to the JUNCS foods.
- Lunch boxes packed only with healthy food should be carried to school if school does not have provision of providing healthy mid-day meal.
- The JUNCS food should not be offered as reward/gift to any child as this gives undue promotion to unhealthy foods.

2. Fruit juices

- Encourage intake of regional and seasonal whole fruits over fruit juices in children and adolescents.
- Fruit juices/fruit drinks/Sugar Sweetened Beverages (SSBs) should not be offered to infants and young children aged below 2 years.
- For children and adolescents (2-18 years) fruit juices, fruit drinks and SSBs should be avoided as far as possible.

- Water should be encouraged as the best drink and should be promoted over fruit juices/drinks at home and school.
- Fruit juices/drinks, if given, should be limited to 125 mL per day for children aged between 2-5 years, and 250 mL per day for age >5 years; and these should preferably be given as fresh juices.

3. Caffeinated drinks

- Caffeinated energy drinks should not be consumed by children and adolescents. Intake of carbonated drinks, tea and coffee is to be completely avoided by children <5 years.
- In school going children and adolescents, tea/coffee intake should be limited to maximum of half cup/day (100 mL) in 5-9 y, and one cup/day (200 mL) in adolescents (10-18 y), provided no other caffeinated products (cola, chocolates) are being consumed.

Recommendations for Schools, Labelling, Advertising, and Marketing

1. Guidelines for Schools

- The recommendations supports Ministry of Women and Child Development recommendations of ban on sale of HFSS foods in school canteens and in near vicinity of 200 meters. It also suggest expanding these recommendations to all the JUNCS foods.
- Efforts to regulate availability of the JUNCS foods in schools must be coupled with ensuring availability and affordability of a variety of healthy snacks and foods in mid-day meals or school canteens.
- School authorities should ensure availability of safe and potable drinking water in schools to reduce consumption of SSBs.
- Ensuring ongoing support, provision of resources, monitoring, feedback and recognition will help to increase the compliance of schools to provide healthy food to children.

2. Guidelines for Labelling

- The recommendations support and advocate traffic light coding of all packaged food as suggested by FSSAI.
 - **Green:** *Always on the menu-* Vegetables and legumes, fruits, grain (cereal) foods; mostly wholegrain and/or high in fiber, lean meat, egg, fish, etc.
 - **Yellow:** *Select carefully-* Approach should be greening, small portion size and reduced frequency: Baked vegetable based snacks, ice creams, milk-based ices and dairy desserts, etc.
 - **Red:** *Not on the menu-* Banned from schools as they are high in fat, salt and sugar: Energy drinks, carbonated and other sweetened beverages, Fried packaged foods, chocolates, potato fries, etc.
- Labelling of nutritional content of packaged foods should be further strengthened.
- The recommendations also supports labelling ‘not suitable for children’ and advocates addition of ‘adolescents’ for unsuitability of caffeinated energy drinks
- The recommendations supports traffic light coding of food available in school canteens, for their nutritional value; and advocates its extension to all packaged/ultra-processed foods in future.

**SAY NO TO
JUNK FOOD**

3. Guidelines for Advertisements

- The recommendations agrees that advertising has strong impact on dietary intake. Advertisement of the JUNCs foods may lead to unhealthy food choices and is likely to be associated with increasing obesity.

- The recommendations recommends legal ban of screen/ print/ digital advertisements of all JUNCS foods for channels/ magazines/ websites/ social media catering to children and adolescents through legislative measures.
- The recommendations recommends ban of branding and use of licensed characters for promoting fast foods/SSBs.
- Advertisements ridiculing healthy foods need to be legally banned.
- The recommendations also recommends screen/ print/ digital advertisements promoting healthy foods for channels catering to children and adolescents and use of licensed characters for branding and promoting healthy foods.

4. Guidelines for Marketing

- The recommendations suggests providing tax discounts on healthy foods and beverages and regulation of discounts on large portions and multiple purchases of the JUNCS foods.
- Differential taxation on the JUNCS and healthy foods/beverages should be considered to promote healthy eating.
- Ensuring availability of variety of healthy food menu at markets/restaurants will give better options for general public, thereby promoting healthy lifestyle.
- Steps should be taken to curb round the clock availability of the JUNCS food on order through mobile Apps.

Keeping in mind the harmful effects of JUNCS on the long term health of children and adolescents, it is prudent to be vigilant. Parents should themselves follow healthy eating habits and serve as role models for children thereby providing them a nutrition sensitive and enabling environment. Meal time should be a, screen and media free, family time which should be enjoyed with healthy fun foods (as differently shaped salads, home grown vegetables, recipes from the

grandmothers book). Parents should ensure a healthy and good breakfast as it is the most important meal of the day. Adolescents and even children should be engaged in helping in the kitchen. Cooking together gives a sense of togetherness in the family and the meal is filled with love and personal touch.

Parents should ensure not to keep junk food at home including cold drinks, instead having fruits is welcome. Junk food should not be used as rewards and parents should try throwing healthy food parties with innovative ideas. Food pyramid should be taken into account while planning the menu for the day, and remembering that it rests on a water bed- which means good intake of water should be encouraged. Teaching children how to eat healthy, is a lesson for life.

Every time you eat is an opportunity to nourish your body.

Let your food be your medicine.

